

The Role of Batam City's Manpower Department in the Protection of Migrant Workers in Batam City

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Abstract

This study examines the role of the Batam City Manpower Office in the protection of migrant workers in the city of Batam, as well as the factors that influence migrant worker protection in the city of Batam. The migration factor reflects the large number of residents from outside the Batam city area who come to work in Batam. Workers from outside of Batam Batam has been designated as an industrial work environment and is supported by BP or the Batam City Concession Agency, according to Presidential Decree No. 113 of 2000 concerning the Batam City Industrial Area. With these regulations and Presidential Decrees, Batam has become an autonomous region, which is now led by the mayor, in accordance with Government Regulation Number 62 of 2019 concerning Batam's Free Trade Zones and Free Ports. The maladministration of unscrupulous migrant worker smugglers in Batam, on the other hand, is documented in a report from the Ombudsman of the Republic of Indonesia representing the Riau Islands, who states that there are unscrupulous migrant workers who come from port officials who help in the process of smuggling migrant workers. According to a qualitative approach, the problem of protecting migrant workers is frequently influenced by issues of authority and the number of government agencies involved.

Keywords: *Batam city's manpower department; illegal workers; migrant workers*

A. Introduction

Batam City, administratively, according to Law Number 53 of 1999, is a municipality that has its own authority or autonomy. Geographically, Batam is a very strategic city because it is located on international shipping lanes and is directly adjacent to neighboring countries, namely Singapore and Malaysia. In this case, according to the Center for Urban Area Development Database, Batam has been a logistics center since 1970 and has become an industrial center in various fields as well as a center for permits for traffic in and out of goods (Batam, 2022). According to Presidential Decree No. 113 of 2000 concerning the Batam City Industrial Area, Batam has been designated as an industrial area work environment and is supported by BP or the Batam City Concession Agency. With these regulations and Presidential Decrees, Batam has become an autonomous region, which is now headed by the mayor based on Government Regulation Number 62 of 2019 concerning Free Trade Areas and Free Ports of Batam.

The number of industries that are growing rapidly in the city of Batam and the increase in migration, or the movement of people from the area to work in the city of Batam, is increasing every year. According to data from the Central Statistics Agency for the city of Batam, the population growth of the city of Batam is increasing. This also causes the rise and fall of the growth rate of migrants in the city of Batam. The following graph shows the growth rate of Indonesian migrant workers in the city of Batam in the last 5 years.

Graph 1.1. Graph of Growth Rate of Indonesian Migrant Workers in Batam City

Source: Batam City Manpower Office, 2022

The graph above illustrates the growth rate of Indonesian migrant workers, which increased by 360 migrants compared to the previous year, which had only 379 migrant workers. Then it decreased drastically due to the COVID-19 pandemic; there were only 37 registered migrant workers in the city of Batam. And in 2021, there will be a moratorium or a COVID-19 pandemic. In 2022, 163 new migrant workers signed up with the Batam City Manpower Office. This was another increase in the number of migrant workers.

The growth rate factor illustrates the large number of residents from outside the Batam city area who come to Batam to look for work. Workers from outside Batam However, the facts on the ground illustrate that not all workers from outside Batam work for complex reasons from various sides, including low levels of education, the quality of workers' insight, and other external factors. This is the background for prospective workers from or outside the Batam area to have the urge to work abroad, such as in neighboring countries like Malaysia or Singapore.

In the Pre-placement Protection Efforts for Indonesian Migrant Workers Abroad, which uses qualitative research methods, the results of the study state that several programs are run

by the Department of Industry and Manpower of Purworejo Regency in an effort to protect Indonesian Migrant Workers abroad, including, among others, socialization, providing passport recommendations, and conducting interviews to explain the rights and obligations of Migrant Workers (Sonhaji, 2020).

So this research is an extension of previous research but has a different perspective and is based on Law Number 18 of 2017 concerning the Protection of Indonesian Migrant Workers and Appendix G of Law Number 23 of 2014 concerning Regional Government, which state that every prospective Indonesian migrant worker has the right to access personal capacity building through education and job training in order to increase their competence, and every Indonesian migrant worker who has returned to Indonesia has the right to protection after work is carried out through the Empowerment of Indonesian Mi So based on the background above, the author takes the research title "The Role of the Batam City Manpower Office in the Protection of Migrant Workers in Batam City."

B. Methods

This is the descriptive research with a qualitative approach. The focus of the research, according to Spradley (Sugiyono, 2015: 209) is a single domain or multiple domains in social situations. The latest information becomes the basis for determining the focus of research obtained from social situations (in the field). So, the focus of this research is on the performance of the Batam City Manpower Office in its role of protecting migrant workers in the city of Batam, and the Batam City Manpower Service is determined as the research point (Sugiyono, 2015).

Opinions about a symptom in qualitative research, according to Sugiyono (2015: 209), are research on the entire social aspect, which includes places, actors, and activities that are related to each other. According to Spradley in Sugiyono (2015: 210): "A focused research refers to a single domain or a few related domains," which means that the focus of a research is a single domain or several domains of the existing social situation (field). The latest information related to social situations is the key to determining the focus of qualitative research (Sugiyono, 2015).

C. Results and Discussion

According to Marry Parker Follet, management is defined as "the art of employing human resources in order to obtain maximum output." Meanwhile, according to J.G. Longenacker, the same book describes the process of managerial activities in making a

decision. Management is an organizational activity that involves the effort of a group of people in an organization to realize its organizational goals with the aim of getting effective and efficient results. In other words, management is the core of the organization. Management includes all aspects of human resources: leadership, policymaking, coordination between people, and the people themselves. Harold Kontz and O' Donnel say in Principles of Management: An Analysis of the Management Function is that management involves things done through and with people, which means management includes achieving goals and includes people. Meanwhile, according to George R. Terry in the book Principles of Management, management is the process of planning, organizing, and supervising by applying other sciences and arts to achieve certain goals (Goraph, 2020).

Then according to M.E. Damask in the book Public Administration, management is a planned approach with the aim of solving problems that occur in individuals or groups, both in the public and private sectors. And William H. Newman, in the book Administrative Action, provides a definition of management as a definition of administration. Mc Farland in the book Management, Principles, and Practice gives the meaning of plan management as carrying out activities to achieve certain goals. And Ordway Tead, in his book The Art of Leadership, defines management as a way of giving direction to activities in the organization to achieve goals (Arif & et al, 2014).

What is meant by "regional government management" are management activities carried out by the authorities with the aim of protecting the right to life and independence, pursuing happiness and peace, and ensuring the people's welfare. The output of good governance is the implementation of development and the development of human resources so that the government runs effectively and efficiently.

Meanwhile, the management function, according to E. McFarland includes planning, organizing, and controlling. Meanwhile, according to Newman (module 5), the functions of management are planning, organizing, gathering resources, monitoring, and controlling. Koontz and O'Donnel provide management functions including planning, organizing, employee formation, job guidance, and supervision. Dan Terry formulated POAC as a management function, which means planning, organizing, acting, and controlling. So, from the understanding of the management function according to the experts above, it can be concluded that the management function includes planning, organizing, compiling employees, directing, and supervising (Arif & et al, 2014).

Local government according to Arif, 2014 literally means the implementation of regional affairs by the local community, which implies that regional affairs or problems are handled by the regional government and not the central government. According to Lockard, local government is a public organization that has the authority and responsibility to manage public policy in a small area and is a subsection of the central government (Arif & et al, 2014).

Meanwhile, according to Green in Arif, 2014, local government is an important instrument of the central government because it implements certain functions that are managed by local communities with the needs, conditions, and characteristics of each region. Maddick provides a definition that local government is a subsection of the central government but is managed by local governments and authorized in terms of administering central government for the regions, such as regulations, taxes, and human resources that are appropriate and still within the scope of the limits provided by the central government.

Local government, according to Gomme in Arif, 2014, is a subdivision of state government whose management is in a system under it that is selected independently from the control of state authorities by competent people in their area, or, in another sense, local governments are still under the control of the government center. So, it can be concluded that local government is a public government that is not hierarchically dependent on the central government in its public service functions (Arif & et al, 2014). According to Muthalib and Khan in Arif, 2014, there are six concepts of local government, namely the social dimension related to two conflicting tendencies, namely the feeling of unity and the unification of the local community and the different feelings of the local residents. The second is the economic dimension, which means two different things: first, that local authorities have minimal resources, so they do not have special authority over socio-economic development; and second, that units in the regions will strengthen local government. The third dimension is the geographical dimension, which means that the area has the interests of its population that are different from other regions. (Arif & et al, 2014)

The fourth dimension is the legal dimension, which relates to regions having their own government that is based on the law for their rights and obligations under the law. In addition, the political dimension implies that local government is a variety of democracy and the openness of people's aspirations. The last dimension is the administrative dimension, which means that local government is a government organization that includes administration, politics, and technology. From the above understanding, according to the expert in state administration at Laiden University, the Netherlands, A. Van Bream stated in his article quote

that the government will run if it pays attention to the long-term interests of its people and gives the people freedom to participate in regulating governance for security and order. So, the government is said to be successful depending on the governance or management of the local government.

Indonesia, which is a country with a large population, does not focus its administrative affairs or interests on the central government alone; the regional governments are given the authority to regulate them in terms of two main interests, namely political interests and administrative interests. According to Rendonelli in the UPB Regional Government Book, "Regional Government" in the community's view is an institution that serves the community to meet their needs so that the Regional Government has its own influence and authority. (Enceng, 2019)

According to E. Koswara Kertapradja, in the relationship between local governments, there are five influencing factors, namely functional, formal, structural, material, cross-sectoral, and operational relationship factors. In the functional relationship, it is stated that there must be a link between vertical agencies and regional offices, and there must be a relationship between programs between one service and another (Enceng, 2019). The formal relationship factor means that there must be a relationship and consistency between one arrangement and another. Third, the structural relationship factor means that in the coordination and implementation activities there must be a linkage in the structural aspect. Fourth, the factor of material and cross-sectoral relations means that if there is a cross-structural program that must be interrelated, dependent, and integrated, and the five factors of operational relations, it means that there is integration between time, funds, location, and other supporting factors so that there is no duplication or disconnection in its implementation.

The functions of the service, which include licensing, public services, and others, are included in the managerial activities of local government. The implementation of good government management, according to Rasyid Thaha is clean management, facilitating the community, and providing certainty. During its implementation, the government makes innovations to provide easy access so that government management activities can be realized properly (Taufik, 2021). Understanding the role, according to Robert Laksana Budi in Muhammad Sawir (2021:26), is a visualization of social interaction by involving parties within the organization. Meanwhile, according to Soekanto according to Sawir, 2021, there is a dynamic dimension based on a person's status after he has carried out his rights and obligations.

According to Friedman, M (2021:12), "role" is the effect of a person's behavior on his social status (Sawir, 2021).

The concept of role according to Komarudin according to Sawir (2021:26) includes the main aspects that are part of the organization or management: attitude toward one's status or position, part of a function in a group or organization, character expected of a person, and a causal correlation that has a function on each variable (Sawir, 2021). Meanwhile, according to Purwanto according to Sawir, (2021:27), the role has characteristics such as decision-making and involvement in carrying out decisions; contributions in various forms, such as ideas, materials, and other forms; work organization sharing roles; groups assigning roles together; and the role of the community being used as a subject (Sawir, 2021).

Meanwhile, the role structure is divided into two, namely, formal roles that include non-heterogeneous attitudes and informal roles that are not real or emotional. Local governments, in carrying out activities, use the bureaucracy as a tool and means of government in the modern era, now with a supervisory function for the public interest. In this case, Max Weber mentions the bureaucracy as an organization with a hierarchy, specialization, roles, and a high level of competence played by trained officials. According to Weber, the bureaucracy has the following roles:

1. Service Function

The government and the ranks of the bureaucracy are dominant, including in describing the national development strategy to be used as a development plan for the short, medium, and long term. The ranks of the bureaucracy have characteristics such as being tough, professional, and reliable. This means that the government must act as an administrative policymaker and implementer of political satisfaction that has been formulated and determined previously.

2. Regulatory or regulatory function

The government is given the authority to implement laws and regulations that have been determined by the legislature through various implementing provisions and policies. The government is intended to manage regularly the work that must be done by many people. Government is said to be good if there are regulations that regulate clear and transparent service procedures.

3. Function as an element of renewal

The government and its staff must have innovations or new ideas while adhering to the principles of effectiveness and efficiency. The role of government must have a strategy

for reform and policy. However, in its implementation, there are factors that hinder, including procedural factors on the institution, a lack of expertise and skills, and non-positive behaviour of bureaucrats or implementers. So, the solution to reduce the existing barriers is to use a flat type of organization, such as a private organization, and temporarily eliminate the pyramidal type of organization (there are a number of powers that make decisions slow and time wasted). The flat type of organization is intended to adapt to today's conditions so that local governments can survive with these adjustments (Dalail, 2015).

According to Friedman, M forms of roles are divided into two types. The first is formal roles that are not heterogeneous in nature, for example, are found in the family environment, such as the role of husband or wife, socialization of children, and so on and the second is informal roles are defined as roles that are not real or visible and are usually related to a person's individual emotions. Moreover, Ngadisajn (2015) implies that the role of the bureaucracy is divided into 4 types such as role in the input process that is the process of providing ideas or ideas for making decisions for a policy in the organization. Second is the role in the decision-making process, as a government bureaucracy, it must have accurate information aimed at final confirmation before decisions or policies are made. Third is the role in acting as a political interpreter, the government bureaucracy must explain the rules clearly and in detail before they are fully implemented. The last is the role in implementing politics. It is defined as the implementation of policies that have been formulated or made. (Dalail, 2015)

The role of the government in other aspects, according to Ritonga in xxxx, includes:

1. Allocative Role

Specifically, the role of government in the allocation of economic resources in order to maximize and efficient production power

2. Distribution Role

It means that the government's role in distributing resources, opportunities, and results evenly according to its capacity

3. Stabilitative Role

Specifically, the role of the government is related to the maintenance of economic stability and its recovery.

4. Dynamic Role

Related to the government's role in the process of accelerating economic growth so that it progresses and develops (Ritonga, 2021).

In the language of labour, a "worker is defined as someone who gets a wage or salary for the results of his work. Migrants are people who move from one place to another. And in terms of workers, migrants are defined as people who move to work abroad. So, it can be concluded that migrant workers are people who work abroad. In the laws and regulations, Indonesian Migrant Workers are known as "Indonesian Migrant Workers," which is defined in Law Number 18 of 2017 concerning the Protection of Indonesian Migrant Workers as every citizen who is working or has worked for wages from outside the territory of the Republic of Indonesia. The law states that there are three types of Indonesian migrant workers: those who work for users with legal entities, those who work for individuals or households, and those who are seafarers, crew members, or in fisheries.

Furthermore, the ILO or International Labour Organization, in Article 11 of the Migration for Employment Convention No. 97 of 1949, migrant workers are defined as someone who moves or has moved from one country to another with the intention of working under another person. Meanwhile, according to the Big Indonesian Dictionary, migrant workers are defined as individuals who move from one place or country to another in order to work for a predetermined period of time. The basis for the protection of migrant workers in Indonesia is guided by the Preamble to the 1945 Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia, which states that the state has the right to protect the entire Indonesian nation and the entire homeland of Indonesia. It is also regulated in the 1945 Constitution, Article 27, Paragraph 2, concerning the right to work and a decent living for every Indonesian citizen. According to the rules of the Act, every worker, including migrant workers, has the right to protection under the auspices of the state.

Problematic factors in local government management include internal and external factors. Internal factors are decentralized democracy and employees. Decentralized democracy greatly impacts decision-making policies and their own management. This is because of the demands of the community in the implementation of public policies, high accountability for the implementation of the principles and performance of human resources (apparatus), and the delegation of authority in decision-making.

In addition, from the internal side of the government, there are several factors that influence, including the disobedience of government officials, the practice of KKN (corruption, collusion, and nepotism), the existence of overlapping cones that result in a lot of budget wastage, governance patterns whose patterns are still unclear, service quality, at least for the public, the lack of state civil apparatus, the fact that there are still countries that want to liberate

their own territory, coordination is difficult, and there is still dependence on the debts of other countries. On the external side, there are several influencing factors, namely globalization and the information technology revolution, namely e-government. Other things that come from external factors include uncertainty in political, economic, social, and cultural factors. From these government management problems, according to Enceng (2019) , there are several excellent strategies, such:

1. Past work is always related to future work.
2. Democratization is still an effective alternative for understanding differences.
3. According to the law, compliance must bring understanding, which is expected to bring the truth.
4. Mature thinking is used as the basis for decision-making.
5. The leadership entrusted to it by its citizens greatly determines the function of government management (Enceng, 2019).

D. Conclusion

To be able to play an effective and efficient role, the Batam City Manpower Office must follow the regulations that have been set by the local government, namely the city of Batam. In addition, the active role and communication with the supervisory agency, the Center for the Protection and Placement of Indonesian Migrant Workers (BP2TKI), and the volunteer network for Indonesian Migrant Workers such as Safe Migrant Batam also need to be improved again so that the protection of Indonesian Migrant Workers can be carried out properly or can be continuously improved.

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